

Brand Loyalty and Advertisement: A Statistical Investigation in Guwahati City for some FMCG Products

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Abstract- Advertisement is a skilful tool and can be used to create market environment and it helps to create demand through convincing. Advertising acts as a powerful instrument to build customer loyalty and assure repeat purchases. In our study we use binary logistic regression and repurchase behaviour to measure loyalty and advertisement effect and found that households are affected by advertisement in different ways.

Keywords- Advertisement, Loyalty programme, FMCG

I. INTRODUCTION

Brand loyalty is the consumer's commitment to repurchase one particular brand of products or services. Brand loyalty exists when customers have a high relative attitude towards the brand which is then exhibited through repurchases behaviour. Every successful business depends on Brand loyalty as it is the ultimate goal aims at. Advertising can be used to create an experimental market environment. Advertisement is a skilful tool and a required factor of marketing mix. A company's distribution may be wide, though it cannot sell by itself. Distribution only makes the express a desire to buy that product before the real sale takes place. Between distribution and consumption, it is advertising which helps to create demand through convincing. The primary function of advertising is to inform. Good advertising helps to build a favourable impression for the product, service and the company. Advertising acts as a powerful instrument to build Customer Loyalty and assure repeat purchases. Advertising is not only confirmed to profit making businesses, but widely used by the government, NGOs and other non-profit organizations including hospitals, unadvertised and educational institutions, political parties and

different social groups. Advertising provides the consumers vital information about different products and helps them make and intuitive choice. From the manufacturer's point of view, advertising is a powerful tool of marketing which helps to create a favourable image for the company and its product. By creating and expanding consumer demand, advertising promotes volume which alone can effectively bring down costs. In a fast developing country like India, advertising not only helps to expand the market but also plays an important role in bringing about changes in social attitudes of the people. The present era is of mass production and mass distribution. Similar products are taken to the market. This involves tight competition amongst the producers. Mainly firms adopt healthy means to maintain their existence in the market. This tendency is a struggle for the producers for their survival in the modern business world. All businessmen aim to make profit by increasing sales at a remunerative price policy. A good quality product of a manufacturer must be known to the public and for this mass communication is needed as the market area is wide. So, manufacturers can adopt sales promotion and advertising as powerful tools to mobilise the marketing machinery. In the present business world, suitable publicity is done through advertising, and

advertisement is a method of publicity. Maffei (1961) presented in his article a new method for studying advertising effects. Demsetz (1962) has discussed the changes in the ratio of nationally advertised brands of frozen orange concentrate to non advertised brands.

Loyalty programmes are other tools for encouraging customers to repeat purchase of different FMCG brands. It is a structured and long-term marketing effort, which provides incentives to repeat customers who demonstrate loyal buying behaviour. Successful programmes are designed to motivate customers in a business's target market to return often, make frequent purchases, and shun competitors.

Objectives

The primary objectives of this study are

- To examine the effect of advertisement on brand loyalty of Fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) with respect to different brand loyalty influencing factors.
- To examine the effect of loyalty programmes on brand loyalty of FMCG products.
- To make a comparative study between the effect of advertisement and loyalty programmes on brand loyalty.

II. METHODOLOGY

Mellens et. al (1966) maintain four categories of brand loyalty measurement. In our study we use one of these four measures in which loyalty is determined by fraction of repeat buyers. Brand loyalty for FMCGs has been represented by the percentage of a buying units purchases going to one brand in a given time period and the number of different brands brought. The data has been analyzed from 2210 households in Guwahati city, Assam which had bought different brands of some FMCG products used in the households in the year 2017 and prior to July 2018 by personal interviews. Effect of socio- economic and demographic factors on brand loyalty with respect to different reasons, viz., price of the product, availability in the market, quality of the product, taste of the product, satisfaction of brand, brand trust and repetition of

followers etc are measured by using binary logistic regression

Binary logistic regression model has been used to estimate the probability of a binary response based on one or more predictors or independent variable

Let Y be a binary response variable, $Y_i = 1$ if the household is loyal to the brand

$= 0$ otherwise.

$X = (X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_k)$ be a set of explanatory variables which can be discrete or continuous.

The logistic regression model is

$$\pi_i = \Pr(Y_i = 1 / X_1 = x_1, X_2 = x_2, \dots, X_k = x_k)$$

$$= \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k)}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k)}$$

The logit transformation is

$$\text{Logit}(\pi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\pi_i}{1 - \pi_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \beta_2 x_{2i} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ki}$$

Thus, the general form of the logit model is

$$\text{Log}(\pi_i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \beta_2 x_{2i} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ki} + U_i$$

Where $\pi_i = P_i / (1 - P_i)$; $P_i = \text{Prob}(Y_i = 1)$

In our context, $P_i = \text{Prob}(Y_i = 1) = \text{Prob. that a household is loyal to a particular brand w.r.t. a loyalty influencing factor. Here, only one (X) explanatory variable has been used, Where,$

$X = 1$, if household is affected by advertisement and $= 0$, otherwise.

The parameters are estimated by method of MLE.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

1. Effect of Advertisement

Considering the effect of advertisement on brand loyalty of FMCGs, it has been observed that out of a total of 2210 households 86.50% households are affected by advertisement and only 13.50% households are not affected by advertisement when all the loyalty influencing factors are ignored. The Figure 4.1 exhibits the share of affected and non affected households by advertisement given in TV/News paper/Poster to make loyal to FMCGs when all loyalty influencing factors such as price of

the product, availability in the market, satisfaction of brand, brand trust, quality of the product and repetition of the followers were excluded. It shows that most of the households were affected by advertisement for choosing a particular brand of FMCG products.

Figure 1: Affected and Non Affected households with respect to Advertisement

Table 1: Effect of advertisement on brand loyalty with respect to market characteristics

Brand loyalty influencing factors		Price of the product		95% C.I. for odds ratio	
	Advertisement (affected households)				
Constant	1.413	-1.924	0.146		
	0.098	0.194	0.146		
	<.01	<.01	0.146		
	4.108		0.146		
				(0.100 0.214)	

Availability in the market	Advertisement (affected households)	-1.858	0.193	<.01	0.158	(0.107 0.228)
	Constant	1.347	0.096	<.01	3.847	
Satisfaction of brand	Advertisement (affected households)	-1.735	0.201	<.01	0.176	(0.119 0.262)
	Constant	1.946	0.117	<.01	7.00	
Brand trust	Advertisement (affected households)	-1.675	0.196	<.01	0.187	(0.128 0.275)
	Constant	1.754	0.109	<.01	5.776	
Quality of the product	Advertisement (affected households)	-1.128	0.211	<.01	0.324	(0.214 0.489)
	Constant	1.932	0.117	<.01	6.905	

Repetition of the followers	Advertisement (affected households)	-2.637	0.250	<.01	0.072	(0.044 0.117)
Constant		0.867	0.084	<.01	2.239	

While considering the different loyalty influencing factors it has come to the observation from Figure 4.1 that most of the households are affected by advertisement.

Figure 2: Affected and Non Affected households by Advertisement w.r.t. different brand loyalty influencing factors

In regard to the different brands of FMCGs (Toothpaste, Beverages and Detergent powder) and the influence of advertisement given in TV/Newspaper/ Poster to make the customers loyal to those brands, it has come to the observations from the Table 4.1 that the households not affected by advertisement are more loyal than others with respect to the loyalty influencing factor price of the product. In other words the customers, who are loyal to a particular brand of FMCG products for the factor price of the product, they are less affected by advertisement. The confidence interval indicates that the odd for households not affected by advertisement is as little as $1/0.214=4.67$ times and as much as $1/0.1=10$ times more than the households affected by advertisement at 95%

confidence. Also the households which are loyal w.r.t. the factor availability in the market, the customers not affected by advertisement are more loyal than those affected by advertisement. The confidence interval indicates that odd for non affected households (by advertisement) are as little as $1/0.228=4.38$ times and as much as $1/0.107=9.34$ times more than affected households at 95% confidence.

While considering the factor satisfaction of brand, brand trust, quality of the product and repetition of followers for choosing different brands of FMCGs, households not affected by advertisement are more loyal (to a particular brand of product w.r.t. proposed loyalty influencing factors) than the households affected by advertisement. The confidence interval indicates that the odd for households not affected by advertisement are as little as $1/0.262=3.81$ times, $1/0.275=3.63$ times, $1/0.489=2.04$ times and $1/0.117=8.55$ times and as much as $1/0.119=8.4$ times $1/0.128) =7.8$ times, $1/0.214=4.67$ times and $1/0.044=22.72$ times more than affected households (by advertisement) for loyalty influencing factors satisfaction of brand, brand trust, quality of the product and repetition of the followers respectively at 95% confidence. In other words we may conclude that the households which are not influenced by advertisement are loyal to a particular brand of FMCG products with respect to all loyalty influencing factors. Thus advertising is a motivating factor to the customers to switch customer's choice from one product to another product. All the interpretations are made based on Table 4.1

2. Effect of Loyalty Programme:

Considering the effect of loyalty programme on brand loyalty of FMCGs, it has been observed that out of a total of 2210 households 85.70% households are affected by loyalty programme and 14.30% households are not affected by loyalty programme without considering all the loyalty influencing factors. The Figure 4.3 exhibits the share of affected and non affected households by loyalty programme. Figure 4.4 represent that most of the households are affected by loyalty programme while considering the different loyalty influencing

factors namely price of the product, satisfaction of brand , availability in the market, quality of the product, brand trust and repetition of followers.

Figure 3: Affected and Non Affected households by the Loyalty programme

Figure 4: Affected and Non affected households by the Loyalty programme w.r.t. different loyalty influencing factors

Table 2: Effect of loyalty programme on brand loyalty with respect to market characteristics

Brand loyalty influencing factors		β	S.E	p value	Odds ratio	95% C.I. for odds ratio
Price of the product	Loyalty programme (affected households)	-2.306	0.20	<.01	0.10	(0.067 0.148)

	Constant	1.525	0.102	<.01	4.593	
Brand trust	Loyalty programme (affected households)	-1.846	0.196	<.01	0.158	(0.108 0.232)
	Constant	1.82	0.112	<.01	6.174	
Satisfaction of brand	Loyalty programme (affected households)	-1.363	0.201	<.01	0.256	(0.173 0.378)
	Constant	1.833	0.113	<.01	6.253	
Availability in the market	Loyalty programme (affected households)	-1.783	0.190	<.01	0.168	(0.116 0.244)
	Constant	1.34	0.096	<.01	3.818	
Quality of the product	Loyalty programme (affected households)	-1.646	0.207	<.01	0.193	(0.129 0.289)

	Constant	2.116	0.126	<.01	8.296	
Repetition of the followers	Loyalty programme (affected households)	-2.197	0.220	<.01	0.111	(0.072 0.171)
	Constant	0.762	0.084	<.01	2.143	

Regarding the effect of loyalty programme on brand loyalty it has come to the observations from Table 4.2 that non- affected households (by loyalty programme) are more loyal than affected households for choosing different brand of FMCG products with respect to loyalty influencing factors price of the product and brand trust. In other words customers that are loyal to a particular brand of product w.r.t. loyalty influencing factors price of the product and brand trust, are less affected by loyalty programme. The confidence interval indicates that the odd for non-affected households are as little as $1/0.148=6.76$ times and $1/0.232=4.31$ times and as much as $1/0.067=14.92$ times and $1/0.108=9.25$ times more than affected households (by loyalty programme) respectively for price of the product and brand trust at 95% confidence. Considering the factor satisfaction of brands households not affected by loyalty programmes are more loyal than affected households. The confidence interval indicates that the odd for non affected households is as little as $1/0.378=2.64$ times and as much as $1/0.173=5.78$ times more than affected households at 95% confidence. Also when considering the loyalty influencing factor availability of the product in the market it has come to the observations from Table5.2 that customers of households not affected by loyalty programme are more loyal than affected customers. The confidence interval for households indicates that the odd for non-affected households

is as little as $1/0.244=4.10$ times and as much as $1/0.116=8.62$ times more than affected households at 95% confidence. Considering the brand loyalty influencing factors quality of the product and repetition of the followers it has been observed that non- affected (by the loyalty programme) households are more loyal than that of affected households. The confidence interval indicates that the odd for non- affected households are as little as $1/0.289=3.46$ times and $1/0.171=5.84$ times and as much as $1/0.129=7.75$ times and $1/0.072=13.88$ times more than affected households respectively at 95% confidence. In other words we may come to an end that the households which are not influenced by loyalty programme are brand loyal to particular FMCG products with respect to all loyalty influencing factors. Thus loyalty programme is also an inspiring factor to the customers to change customer's choice from one brand to another brand. All the interpretations are made based on Table 4.2.

IV. CONCLUSION

The major revelations that may be drawn from the study go as follows:

- The study revealed that most of the households are affected by advertisement and loyalty programmes for choosing a particular brand of FMCGs product when all the loyalty influencing factors have been ignored.
- The households not affected by advertisement are more loyal than that of other household affected by advertisement with respect to all considered loyalty influencing factors.
- The households those are loyal with respect to price of the product, availability in the market, satisfaction of brand, brand trust, quality of the product and repetition of followers are less affected by advertisement.
- Regarding the effect of loyalty programmes on households for choosing a particular brand of FMCG products, non affected households (by loyalty programme) are more loyal than that of affected households for all suspected loyalty influencing factors.
- It has been observed from the comparative study that effects of both the advertisement

and loyalty programme on the households are almost same for different loyalty influencing factors for choosing a particular brand of FMCG products.

- Finally, it can be concluded that the advertisement and the loyalty programme have significant impact on brand loyalty. The customers having no influence of advertisement are purchasing same commodity repeatedly. In other words, they are more loyal to a particular product than the customers having advertising effect. The similar observation has been noticed in case of loyalty programmes also.

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